

Education and the Three-City Problem of Modern Life

Jeff Frank

Abstract

This paper offers an introduction to Luke Burgis’s articulation of the three-city problem of modern life, arguing that this problem should concern educators more than it currently does. I focus on challenges and opportunities presented by the three-city problem, suggesting that educators can view their work as a poetics of value creation. By conceptualizing their work in the terms set by Burgis, teachers can activate their agency and the agency of their students. This offers educators new hope and a way of responding to artificial intelligence and other emerging technologies.

Keywords

philosophy of education, education, pedagogy, Three-City Problem, Luke Burgis, Charles Taylor, Jonathan Sacks, Technology and Education, Poetics of Teaching

Introduction

Luke Burgis’s (2022) paper “The Three-City Problem of Modern Life,” while published in a popular magazine, offers an illuminating perspective on an issue educators should care about. Burgis argues that just as the early Christian church wrestled with the relationships between Athens (reason) and Jerusalem (faith), inhabitants of the modern world face a third center of gravity: Silicon Valley. This new city should cause us to ask the question: How do Athens, Jerusalem, and Silicon Valley relate to one another? According to Burgis, there is a temptation to live *as if* it were possible to avoid the pull of any one of these cities. For example, closing the gates of Athens to Jerusalem and Silicon Valley. But Burgis thinks this is impossible. And for this reason, Burgis urges us to live at the intersections of these three cities, charting a digital life that is guided by the values of faith and reason, a life of reason open to faith and technological advances, and a faith life that is open to reason and technology.

What I find most compelling about Burgis’s argument is his call for us to take philosophical anthropology seriously. While Athens and Jerusalem have well-developed visions of the human person, Silicon Valley’s approach to the human is emerging as it goes along. Silicon Valley, according to Burgis, is guided by an urge to create value. It moves quickly and breaks things, leaving transformed humans in its wake. Our digital lives, according to Burgis (2021), are transforming our desires, often without our explicit consent or even conscious awareness.

We find ourselves purchasing things we don't need, spending hours scrolling content that isn't upbuilding, outsourcing our agency to an algorithm that may not care about anything other than our continued engagement with our devices (Song 2021). Pornography and looksmaxxing (Wise 2026) have become billion-dollar industries, and artificial intelligence creeps into corners of our life that we thought were immune to technological influence. Many young people find the digital world overwhelming (Lipsky 2018), and yet they cannot find an outside. As digital natives, they struggle to find their way back into the orbits of reason and religion. Unlike Athens and Jerusalem, cities built on questions and distributed authorities who can easily be engaged with, Silicon Valley feels more distant even though we carry its ethos in our hands. Many of our best technologies are running in the background of our lives, immune from rational and spiritual critique or even full conscious understanding. This poses special problems for educators. We know how to critique and intellectually engage with Athens and Jerusalem, but we struggle to engage with Silicon Valley in pedagogically enriching ways. We've adopted and utilized the tools of Silicon value, and we are only now beginning to appreciate that these tools are not neutral (Borgmann 2003). They are forming us, even though we are unclear how we could either reject or fully embrace these tools, understanding and appreciating their full implications for our ethical, intellectual, and spiritual lives.

Burgis urges us to live at the intersection of the three-cities, and yet I worry that it will be tremendously difficult for a digital native to desire leaving Silicon Valley once they've accustomed themselves to its conveniences and affordances. And this is the key point of my paper. How can educators and those concerned with education guide digital natives to the intersections of these three cities? Clearly, we must model this kind of engagement ourselves by placing ourselves in the tensions and possibilities that emerge between these cities. But we need to do more than this. We need to find ways to make the journey appealing, and to do this, we need articulate the guiding virtues of Athens and Jerusalem, making them come alive for young people who may have never felt their pull.

Humility, Obedience, and Adventure in an Era of Personalization

One striking vision of the human that is emerging from Silicon Valley is personalization. If the vision of Athens is the ever-questioning Socrates seeking truth (Arendt 1971), and if the vision of Jerusalem is the adoring worshiper seeking God (Ross 2013), then the vision of Silicon Valley is the user being fed content that is designed to be tailored to them. One way the Catholic Church has found the intersection of faith and reason is through the virtue of humility and obedience (McCabe 1984). The scholar and the worshiper are both humble before something that is wholly outside of their control (Rosa 2020, 2024). Residents of Athens, the scholar and the scientist, are trained to undermine their assumptions and best thinking through constant questioning and engagement with others who hold competing views. Similarly, religious adherents work to discern God's purpose, seeking to attune themselves to God (Fishbane 2008), even if this means undergoing dramatic transformations in the process (Brother John 2021). By contrast, personalization feeds a self-focus verging on solipsism. A user opens an app or does

a search, and the results are tailored to the user's search history and digital footprint. Because the app wants user-engagement, it doesn't provide the user with anything that risks breaking that engagement. In the process, the virtue of humility atrophies, and habits of convenience are built. The user becomes a consumer, not a seeker undergoing the disciplines of humility, aspiring to the Good, the True, and the Beautiful (Guardini 1998).

This presents educators with a key challenge. A digital native is used to having content fed to them. They are used to reacting to content with a thumbs up or a thumbs down, training an algorithm to tee up more content that meets the user's approval. This is not the way a native of Athens or Jerusalem lives. Socrates is a gadfly who stings interlocutors awake. As Pope Francis taught, Caravaggio's *The Calling of St. Matthew* is a message for us (Farago 2025). We are each, like Matthew, summoned to die to that which is deadening, taking the risks of discipleship. As we know, Socrates and Christ were put to death. Living a life of aspiration is a perpetual challenge that each age will find ways to avoid. How much more so in our age, an age marked by ubiquitous technologies designed to keep users endlessly tethered to our devices?

Two points are worth making here. The first is that educators who themselves are believers also believe that God made the human for a relationship with God. There is a restlessness built into the human that will not rest until it finds this relationship with God (Williams 2016). Educators who are also believers, can rely on the faith that this is true, and then use this faith to continue hoping, with charity, that our students will eventually come to realize the limitations of their lives with devices. Educators at home in Jerusalem don't have to force this point judgmentally. This leads to the second point. People deeply immersed in their devices are beginning to grow bored and weary (Gary 2022). They are becoming critical of their lives with technology, wondering what it would be like to live a life with more agency. As technology companies come under increased scrutiny for practices that aim to manipulate and trap users, more young people will look for alternatives to a life lived solely in the confines of Silicon Valley.

Educators can demonstrate how the cities of Athens and Jerusalem are premised on genuine adventure, where technology may often only give the appearance of adventure. There is an irony or paradox here worth exploring (Smith 1987). Obedience, either to something like the scientific method or methods of scholarship, and obedience to religion are often dismissed as limiting freedom. As such, a technological device that offers unlimited personalized recommendations can feel much more liberating. And yet, as anyone who submits, obediently, to the disciplines of Athens and Jerusalem learns, discipline leads to freedom. Not freedom from discipline, but freedom for excellence (Pinckaers 2003, 65-81). This is the adventure. A scholar or a worshipper cannot command results through sheer will alone (Farber 2000, 75-158). But they can cultivate disciplines that makes it more likely that they will experience a spiritual or intellectual breakthrough. They learn to balance proactivity with receptivity, ready to receive, encounter, and engage with the Truth when it appears.

A device, by contrast, can be commanded. A user doesn't need to discipline themselves or make room for receptivity to be an effective user of the device. And because of this, the device

cannot offer genuine adventure. Devices do offer access to worlds of information that can be very useful to the resident of Athens or Jerusalem, but devices are built to be fully operational for any and every user, regardless of how disciplined or receptive they are. Here, I think, is an opportunity for educators. We nudge students to the intersections of these three cities by reminding students of the tool-like nature of technology, reminding them that these tools are not ends: they must point beyond themselves. And what they can point to are the traditional values and virtues of Athens and Jerusalem, with humility and obedience at the forefront. While these words can sound like the opposite of freedom, the task of the educator is to show that humility and obedience are in the service of adventure. In the final section I draw out what one adventure at the intersections of the three cities might look like.

A Poetics of Value Creation?

“The Three-City Problem of Modern Life” argues that Silicon Valley is a unique center of gravity because it, according to Burgis and unlike Athens and Jerusalem, is primarily focused on value creation. This is a euphemism, of course, for wealth: Silicon Valley is creating vast wealth. But it means much more than this as well. Silicon Valley has unleashed all kinds of content creators, some human and some driven by artificial intelligence. The world is being flooded with new content, which unleashes new desires. Athens and Jerusalem can help a young person build the discernment necessary to navigate this new content and these new desires, but Athens and Jerusalem might also learn from the ways that Silicon Valley has unleashed new possibilities for value creation, possibilities that young people are clearly resonating with.

Sociologist and critical theorist Harmut Rosa (2020, 2021, 2024) argues that late-stage capitalism acts as a treadmill that effaces itself and undermines possibilities of critique. Like a new form of religion, Silicon Valley is amassing devotees, often devotees who are unaware that they are bound to the ideals of practices of technologists and other digital entrepreneurs. As Burgis notes (2022), citing musical artist Bob Dylan, we all “gotta serve somebody.” Or, as Walter Benjamin (2005) forcefully argues, capitalism has become its own form of religion, but a religion without hopes of redemption. The histories of Athens and Jerusalem are far longer than that of Silicon Valley, and so it is easy to believe that Silicon Valley doesn’t have the center of gravity the other cities do. But this is a mistake. We worship our devices and outsource our thinking to these devices. They are forming us in much the same ways that religious devotion and schooling form us. A digital native may spend more time with and on their device than engaged with any other source of influence or insight.

Although René Girard is Burgis’s (2026) touchstone source, I find that Charles Taylor (1992, 2018, 2026) is also a good guide when we think about appeals of Silicon Valley. Taylor draws attention to the appeals and limitations of the ideal of authenticity, suggesting that our secular age is one where young people are motivated and drawn to the goods of self-expression. Under this way of thinking, Athens and Jerusalem are appealing if they can further the goods of self-expression. Silicon Valley understands this, and gives young people almost unlimited

opportunities for self-expression. Taylor suggests, though, that Silicon Valley eventually comes to feel empty if it loses touch with sources and traditions that give shape to self-expression, and—like Burgis—urges us to find self-expression through tradition, allowing traditions to shape and modify our ideals and modes of expression.

We must become more aware of how we are being formed, and when we are outsourcing our agency to devices. We need to relearn the virtues of humility that facilitate adventure, intellectually forming ourselves around values that we assent to upon thoughtful and careful reflection. Rather than letting technologies and technologists form us without our consent or full understanding, Silicon Valley must become an object of criticism, and our devices and applications must be made tools that serve our values, not the thing that shapes our values, forming selves and our understanding of what it means to be a self in the process.

Conclusion

I will close by suggesting that we can think about education at the intersection of Burgis's three-cities as a poetics (Hansen 2004, 119). A poet who uses traditional forms without cultivating their unique voice will come to feel as un compelling as a poet who only speaks from personal experience without an interest in learning from and engaging with the long traditions of poetry. As Rabbi Jonathan Sacks (2019) notes, a religious life is one that lives at the intersection of human responsibility and proactivity on the one hand, and what John Keats calls negative capability on the other. Silicon Valley brings new energy to how we can become proactive, and we residents of Athens and Jerusalem can use this energy to help the next generation remain receptive to long traditions of thought that will allow for richer expression. As Taylor teaches, authenticity comes through tradition, not in avoidance of it. Burgis's articulation of the three-city problem welcomes educators to stand at the intersection of these three cities, calling us to continual conversion. When we become too comfortable in one city—faith, reason, technology—we should engage the others. Standing in the tensions these cities will continually generate, we will develop new forms of pedagogy and new ways to invite our students to live with meaning, purpose, and integrity. Poetically, we can create value through living these three-city tensions.

Much of the excitement new technologies generate center on the promise that we can become creators, and that we can engage directly with other creators. Silicon Valley has unleashed worlds of content and content creators. In addition to teaching how we can exercise discernment in these new worlds, educators formed by Athens and Jerusalem can also be reminders and witnesses (Hansen 2025) to the ways that humility and obedience can be adventures. Just like the poet who exercises and expands their negative capability while cultivating their voice, we can show students that ease and convenience block the discipline of learning what something means. A poetics of value creation means making room for the world, learning the discipline of how to listen to what the world has to teach, and only then considering what is worth adding to the conversation of humankind (Oakeshott 1989). The world doesn't need more hot takes and immediate reactions. The world needs the voice of the young, a voice that will not emerge automatically and that is being threatened and anaesthetized by the

overinfluence of Silicon Valley. By helping each emerging generation stand at the intersection of the three-cities, we may—unlike Oedipus at the crossroads (Lear 1998)—poetically create insight into the riddle of being and attempting to become human that moves from the dead ends of knowingness and technological treadmills and into what Jonathan Lear (2006) calls radical hope.

Educators have an especially important role to play. We should neither assess students on inert knowledge that is meaningless to them nor attempt to endlessly entertain them with screens. School can be a place of disciplined interest, where students learn how to listen and how to add their voice to the ongoing conversations of humanity. For this to happen, though, educators need to facilitate engagement that always points beyond itself. Even as each moment in the classroom should be compelling for students, the goal is not entertainment. Rather, students should be given intimations of how much more meaningful their lives and our world becomes when they care enough to humbly engage in the adventure of poetically engaging with and creating value. And when they do this, they move out of the state of being a digital native, and live the generative tensions of the three-city problem of modern life.

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Jeff Frank, Ph.D.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1955-7063>

St. Lawrence University

Education Department

23 Romoda Dr, Canton, NY 13617

United States

jfrank@stlawu.edu